

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 1 |
January 2022 | Monthly Journal
by TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Effects of Packaging Materials on Shelf Life and Post-harvest Quality of Bell Peppers (*Capsicum annuum cv Indra*) under Ambient Conditions

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Accepted

January 09,2022

Published

February 22,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); **Conflicts of Interest:** There are no conflicts to declare.

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Funding:

None

How to cite this article (APA) Nisha Paneru (2022). Effects of Packaging Materials on Shelf Life and Post-harvest Quality of Bell Peppers (*Capsicum annuum cv Indra*) under Ambient Conditions. *North American Academic Research*, 5(1), 174-189. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6210385>

ABSTRACT

Even though capsicum is considered non-climacteric fruit, it still progresses through a normal ripening process and undergoes high respiration and transpiration rate after harvest. The physiological weight loss, shortened shelf life, and quality deterioration during storage have become a serious predicament to many capsicum stakeholders. The study was conducted to determine the best packaging material to expand shelf life and improve the quality of capsicum. The fresh bright green color capsicum of cultivar Indra was harvested and packed in different packaging materials, namely polypropylene- PP (25 μ and 50 μ), low-density polyethylene- LDPE (25 μ and 50 μ), cardboard box, jute sack, and open tray. The experiment was carried out in a Completely Randomized Design in three replications. Physical, biochemical, and subjective parameters of capsicum were assessed in every five days. The packaging materials significantly checked weight loss and maintained quality attributes like total soluble solids, titratable acidity, pH, firmness, and ascorbic acid content during storage. The capsicum packed in PP 50 μ films remained marketable for 34.64 days and showed minimum percentage weight loss throughout the storage followed by LDPE 50 μ for 32.67 days. In contrast, control fruits became unmarketable after 17.33 days exhibiting maximum percentage weight loss all over. Plus, capsicum packed in PP 50 μ film offered better pH and ascorbic acid content while those in LDPE 50 μ film retained better TSS, TA, and firmness.

Keywords

CAPSICUM, LOW-DENSITY POLYETHYLENE, POLYPROPYLENE, PHYSIOLOGICAL WEIGHT LOSS, QUALITY ATTRIBUTES, SHELF LIFE

1. Introduction

Bell pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.), an extensively cultivated and consumed vegetable crop in the world, has risen into the category of high-value crops due to its superior taste, therapeutic properties, high yield and return per unit area. People thoroughly enjoy consuming capsicum for its versatility, glossy different colored texture and blending aromatic flavor. Inevitably, the world production and consumption of capsicum have been gradually increasing since 2000 [1]. The major factors driving the capsicum market across the globe are the increasing use of bell pepper in daily cooking, food processing industry, and the pharmaceutical industry [2]. While the demand and foreign trade of capsicum are surging, the grave concern for prolonging the post-harvest life is also surfacing. Like any other vegetable, bell pepper also undergoes post-harvest loss and quality deterioration. It is estimated that it has an estimated loss of 22.54% owing to flaccidity, decay, wilting, and discoloration [3]. Besides, microorganism contamination, heavy metals pollution, and pesticide residues are also major problems. As a result, farmers, retailers, and small traders are facing huge financial losses. Hence, minimizing these postharvest losses is of paramount importance for food security, economic growth, and welfare of the society.

In general, at the farmer and retail level, capsicums are kept blatantly in an unpackaged form under ambient conditions. This type of market handling significantly reduces shelf life and quality if not sold immediately. These existing postharvest losses could be remarkably decreased with the adoption of an improved packaging system [4]. Moreover, the advancing concept of supermarkets and displaying capsicum in the super retail outlets for attraction have made packaging inevitable components for safe post-harvest handling and storage. Proper packaging not only protects against microbial contamination, bruising, physical injury, and weight loss but also restricts respiration rate, ripening, and ethylene production [5]. Plus, packaging maintains uniformity and visual quality of capsicum as well, which have a significant effect on consumer preferences.

The right selection of packaging material is indispensable for maintaining the quality and freshness of capsicum. The preferences of packaging material mostly vary on nature of produce, duration of storage, distance of transportation, and nature of the display. Different types of packaging materials such as pallets bins, wire-bound crates, pulp containers, paper and mesh bags, plastic bags, and shrink wraps are found across the market. Among all, plastic bags are the predominant material for fruit and vegetable packaging including capsicums, mostly due to their transparency, affordability, heat and chemical resistivity, and internal atmospheric modification. Likewise, the choice of plastic also varies between High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), Polypropylene (PP), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), Polystyrene, and Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET, PETE). Hence, there was a need to determine the best possible packaging materials for demanding crops like capsicum. Therefore, this study was aimed at the investigation of the effectiveness of different packaging materials in extending the shelf life of the capsicum with the

specific objective to compare the impact of those materials on the physical and biochemical properties of capsicum.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental site

The experiment was carried out under ambient conditions at the horticultural laboratory of Agriculture and Forestry University, located in Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal at the latitude of 27° 59' N, the longitude of 84° 34' E and an altitude of 385 m above sea level. During the time of the experiment, the site got monthly precipitation of 25.98 mm, mean maximum and minimum temperature of 18°C and 3°C with approximately 7 rainy days. The relative humidity of the site varied from 45% to 78% and maximum was obtained during the morning while minimum at midday.

2.2. Experimental materials

Fresh green matured Indra variety of capsicum were harvested at horticultural maturity stage manually avoiding mechanical damage from Green Agrotech Pvt. Ltd. The fruits were transported immediately to the laboratory in plastic crates. The samples were then graded by size and shape and one with defects was discarded. The unblemished uniform capsicums were washed with tap water following 1% CaCl₂ solution to remove field heat, soil particles and prevent microbial growth. Low-density polyethylene (LDPE) bags (25μ and 50 μ), polypropylene (PP) bags (25μ and 50 μ), Cardboard box (20× 10×10) mm, jute sack, and plastic crates (as a control) were used as packaging materials.

2.3. Experimental designs

The treatment consisted of seven packaging materials; low-density polyethylene (LDPE) bags (25μ and 50 μ), polypropylene (PP) bags (25μ and 50 μ), Cardboard box (20× 10×10) mm, jute sack, and plastic crates (as a control). The experiment was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications and a total of 21 experimental units. Each treatment had 2 kg capsicums.

2.4. Data collection

The data for all treatments were collected every 5 days interval over a storage period. The sample of capsicum fruits was taken randomly from each treatment for assessment of physical and chemical parameters. Physical, chemical, and subjective data taken during the storage period were as follows:

2.4.1. Temperature and relative humidity

The assessment of both temperature and relative humidity was done using a humidity hygrometer (RTEK-1 model) throughout the storage period.

2.4.2. Physiological weight loss

The weight loss was determined using a digital balance (Krishna, kss-48 model) having an accuracy of 0.1g. The physiological loss in weight was calculated as the difference between the initial weight and the weight at the time of measurement and expressed as a percentage (% of initial weight).

$$\text{PWL (\%)} = \frac{W_0 - W_1}{W_0} \times 100$$

Where W_0 = initial weight and W_1 = final weight

2.4.3. Firmness

The texture firmness of stored capsicum was measured with a penetrometer (GY-3 model) having an insertion depth of 10mm and a pressure diameter of 8mm.

2.4.4. Total soluble solids (° Brix)

Randomly selected capsicum was cut into slices and juice was taken out by blending into juice blender. The TSS was calculated by placing a drop of juice on the lens of a hand-held refractometer (HSR-500 model).

2.4.5. pH

The pH of capsicum juice was measured by a portable digital pH meter (VicTsing). To increase the accuracy, the pH meter was periodically calibrated with buffer at pH 4.01 and 6.86 before taking the measurements.

2.4.6. Titratable acidity

The TA content of capsicum juice was estimated by titration method using standardized 0.1 N NaOH solution and phenolphthalein indicator (2-3 drops) and calculated as percent citric acid. The volume of 0.1 N NaOH was used to neutralize the acid content in the sample and multiply it by a correction factor of 0.064 to estimate titratable acidity as a percentage of citric acid. At first, three drops of phenolphthalein were added into 5 ml of capsicum juice solution present in a conical flask. Then, NaOH solution was added from the burette in a controlled manner until the color of the solution in the flask changed to pink. The amount of NaOH used to change color was recorded from the graduated burette. The percent titratable acidity was calculated by using the formula

$$\text{Titratable acidity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Volume of NaOH used} \times \text{Normality of NaOH} \times 0.064}{\text{Volume of juice titrated}} \times 100$$

Where Acid milliequivalents (mEq) factor for citric acid is 0.064,

2.4.7. Ascorbic acid (Vit C)

Vitamin C content of capsicum was estimated by a volumetric method as mentioned by Sadasivam and Manickam (1996). Here, 5ml of working standard solution was taken in a conical flask to which, the 10ml of 4% oxalic acid solution was added and was titrated against dye solution (V_1 ml) (2,6-dichloroindophenol) until the solution turned to pink color. After that, the sample and 4% oxalic acid solution was centrifuged, then pipetted out 5ml of supernatant, to which 10ml of 4% oxalic acid was added and titrated against the dye (V_2 ml). Thus, the formula used to calculate the Vit C content is

$$\text{Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)} = \frac{0.5\text{mg} \times V_2 \times 100 \times 100}{V_1 \times 5\text{ml} \times \text{weight of sample}}$$

Where V_1 = amount of dye consumed during the titration V_2 = amount of dye consumed when the supernatant was titrated with 4% oxalic acid

2.5. Statistical analysis

The experimental data for all parameters were analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) techniques based on Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with the help of the statistical software GenStat. The mean of the data was obtained from a replicate reading of each experiment and mean differences were carried out by Duncan's multiple range test at a 5% level of significance.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Biochemical Properties

Table 1 Effect of different packaging materials in mean TSS, TA, Vit C, pH, and firmness of bell pepper

Treatments	TSS	TA	Vit C	pH	Firmness
T1 (LDPE 25 μ)	2.25 ^c	0.54 ^b	39.04 ^b	5.97 ^{ab}	3.10 ^{bc}
T2 (LDPE 50 μ)	1.9 ^c	0.69 ^a	42.24 ^{ab}	5.85 ^{ab}	4.81 ^a
T3 (PP 25 μ)	2.68 ^{bc}	0.51 ^b	37.93 ^{bc}	6.24 ^{ab}	2.33 ^c
T4 (PP 50 μ)	2.17 ^c	0.63 ^a	45.32 ^a	5.31 ^b	4.08 ^{ab}
T5(Cardboard box)	2.84 ^{bc}	0.44 ^{bc}	33.77 ^c	6.64 ^a	2.21 ^c
T6 (Jute Sack)	3.63 ^{ab}	0.41 ^{bc}	32.74 ^c	6.51 ^a	2.16 ^c
T7 (Open tray)	4.33 ^a	0.34 ^c	29.42 ^d	6.67 ^a	2.00 ^c
SEM	0.342	0.061	1.52	0.29	0.378
LSD _{0.05}	1.038 ^{**}	0.185 ^{***}	4.61 ^{***}	0.886 [*]	1.14 ^{***}
CV (%)	21	23.3	15	8.3	22.1

SEM, Standard Error of mean; CV, Coefficient of Variation; LSD, Least Significant Difference. Means in the column with the same letter (s) in superscript indicate no significant difference between treatments at 0.05 level of significance; '***' Significant at 0.001 level of Significance; '**' Significant at 0.01 level of Significance; '*' Significant at 0.05 level of Significance

3.1.1 Total soluble solids

The Total Soluble Solid (TSS) is considered as a primary quality attribute of capsicum as high TSS content enhances the flavor and palatability of the fruit. The changes in TSS content of capsicum fruits during the time of storage are displayed in table 1. There was a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect of different packaging materials on the TSS values of capsicum which mean varied between 4.33 to 1.9° Brix under ambient conditions. In general, TSS showed a trend of initial increase up to 20 days and decrease thereafter (fig1). The highest mean TSS (4.33° Brix) was noted in capsicum kept in open tray followed by jute sack (3.63° Brix) and the lowest mean was observed in LDPE 50 μ (1.9° Brix) which was found statistically similar with PP 50 μ (2.17° Brix) and LDPE 25 μ (2.25° Brix) packaging materials. The rise in this parameter during storage could be potentially caused by moisture loss, hydrolysis of polysaccharides, and concentration of juice as a result of degradation. Likewise, low TSS observed in capsicum packed in LDPE and PP materials may be probably due to maintenance of humid micro-climate inside these films, therefore retarding ripening and leading to slow hydrolysis of starch, pectic acid, proteins, and fats and thereby decreasing TSS [7]. Almost, the comparable outcome was seen in a study conducted by González and Tiznado (1993), where capsicum kept openly showed a relatively rapid increment in TSS in comparison to capsicum packed in LDPE materials with each passing day. However, at the end of storage, a sharp decrement in TSS was also observed (fig 1), owing to the natural phenomena such as respiration and metabolism that gradually use the product of hydrolysis as their substrate. Overall, the treatments which exhibited low TSS during storage were considered to be less optimal as this fruit is mostly used in salad making, where flavor and palatability are must. So, the capsicum with high TSS is highly preferred. Hence, packaged capsicums do not rapidly deplete their soluble solids as those of control capsicums as depicted in this study.

Figure 1 Effect of packaging materials in total soluble solids of bell pepper cv Indra at different days of storage

3.1.2. Titratable acidity

Figure 2 Effect of packaging materials in titratable acidity of bell pepper cv Indra at different days of storage

Titratable acid (TA) measures total organic acid concentration, which is a very crucial parameter that greatly influences the taste, aroma, color, and overall stability of capsicum. In this study, a highly significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect of different packaging materials was observed at the time of storage on TA of capsicum (table 1). The mean TA value varied from 0.34% to 0.69% under ambient storage conditions. The lower TA value of capsicum was noted in an open tray (0.34%) and capsicum packed in LDPE 50 μ (0.69%) showed the highest TA which was statistically at par with PP 50 μ (0.63%). Generally, TA of capsicum showed the trend of gradual decrease with the advancement in storage days as shown in figure 2. The decrement in the acidity level of capsicum could be attributed to the use of free organic acids present in the vacuole of cells during various metabolic processes like respiration and anthocyanin biosynthesis, and also by conversion of acids into sugars at the time of storage [9]. Likewise, the higher loss of TA in the open tray might be due to the depletion of free organic acids as a result of relatively faster respiration and metabolic activities than other treatments. On the other hand, the higher TA value of LDPE and PP-packed fruits could be explained by the reduced rate of respiration due to the lesser availability of oxygen. Moreover, as capsicum respire, the O₂ level gradually decreases and the level of CO₂ increases inside the films. These atmospheric conditions might directly retard the consumption of respiratory substrates like organic acids and sugars. Consequently, maintaining high acidity in capsicum is considered very pleasant as it helps in flavor retention of capsicum. These findings are in close agreement with the results reported by Kirad et al. (2007) who reported the response of different packaging materials and chemicals on the shelf life of strawberries. Nath et al. (2012) also reported maximum

acidity levels in LDPE non-perforated and PP non-perforated packed fruits, in contrast, to control pears. Thus, LDPE and PP packaging materials tended to retain more acidity during storage.

3.1.3. pH

Figure 3 Effect of packaging materials in pH of bell pepper cv Indra at different days of storage

pH quantifies the hydronium ions concentration in a fruit, which is fundamental to assess the ability of a microorganism to grow and the tendency of fresh fruit to prolong its shelf life [12]. The data in Table 1 reveal a statistically significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) of different packaging materials on the pH of stored capsicum. Additionally, fig 3 describes changes in pH during the storage period of capsicum. The pH decreases somewhat initially at day 5 and then eventually showed a gradual upsurge with an increase in storage days under all packaging treatments. The mean pH values of capsicum range between 6.67 to 5.31 particularly. The maximum pH value was found in the control treatment (6.67), closely followed by the cardboard box (6.64) and jute sack (6.51). Correspondingly, a minimum pH value was seen in PP 50 μ packed capsicum (5.31). The early dip in pH value or increase in acidity of capsicum in beginning days could be associated with the production of acids from the catabolism of sugar under ambient conditions, whereas, the subsequent rise of pH in latter days might be attributed to a reduction of TA and increase in TSS of capsicum. The higher pH value and lower acidity in control could be explained by the increase in the rate of use of acids as a respiratory substrate under open ambient conditions resulting in depletion of acidity. Contrarily, the lowest pH value and highest acidity in PP 50 μ packaging material could be due to the relatively lower respiration rate inside film owing to its modified condition. The comparable outcome was reported by Azene et al., (2014) in papaya fruit. Almost the majority of microorganisms grow and proliferate around neutral pH values (6.5-7.0). Therefore, PP and LDPE films can plausibly consider effective.

3.1.4. Firmness

Figure 4 Effect of packaging materials in firmness of bell pepper cv Indra at different days of storage

Firmness is yet another essential quality attribute in the consumer acceptability of capsicum and its assessment helps in the evaluation of capsicum susceptibility to physical or mechanical damage. The data pertaining to significant variation ($p \leq 0.05$) of different packaging materials in flesh firmness of capsicum is presented in table 1. Generally, the firmness followed a declining trend in accord with advancement in storage time in capsicum (fig4). Meanwhile, declination was by far faster in control capsicum than packaged capsicum. The mean firmness value in this study varies from 4.81 kgf/cm² to 2 kgf/cm². The capsicum packed in LDPE 50μ maintained the highest firmness of 4.81 kgf/cm² and was at par with PP 50μ of 4.08 kgf/cm². Likewise, control fruits registered the lowest firmness of 2 kgf/cm² and found statistically similar with jute sack (2.16kgf/cm²), cardboard (2.21kgf/cm²) and PP 25μ (2.33 kgf/cm²). The gross softening of capsicum as the storage time progressed could be the consequences of texture modification following the degradation of polysaccharides namely, pectin, hemicellulose, and cellulose during ripening. It could also be accountable to loss of water from peel to pulp via osmosis resulting in flaccidity development [14]. Likewise, it might also be attributed to the reduction in middle lamella cohesion due to the high activity of the endopolygalacturonase enzyme [15]. The relatively most firmed capsicum was seen in PP and LDPE packages, feasibly due to the effects of films in maintaining high humidity and CO₂ inside it, contributing to maximum retention of turbidity and minimum loss of water and polysaccharide degradation. On the contrary, a higher rate of softening in control capsicum could be because of the higher rate of respiration, hastening ripening process, and increment in moisture loss in open conditions. A similar finding for capsicum was reported by Sahoo et al., (2014a) where maintenance of higher turgid texture was seen in PP-packed capsicum.

3.1.5. Ascorbic acid

Figure 5 Effect of packaging materials in the ascorbic acid content of bell pepper cv Indra at different days of storage

Ascorbic acid is not only accountable for the high nutritional value and antioxidant properties of the capsicum but also contributes to the overall acidity of the fruit [17]. Therefore, ascorbic acid retention is pivotal during storage. The perusal of data recorded during the period of the study revealed the significant ($P \leq 0.05$) variation of different treatments on the ascorbic acid content of capsicum (table 1). The ascorbic acid content of the fruit increased initially for 5 days, then experienced a linear decline in all treatments as the storage period advanced (Fig 5). The mean ascorbic acid value in this study ranged from 29.42mg/100g to 45.32mg/100g. The control capsicum (29.42mg/100g) had the lowest AA value, whereas, PP 50 μ packaged capsicum attained the highest (45.32mg/100g) AA value which was found statistically similar with LDPE 50 μ packaged capsicum (42.24mg/100g). It was noticed that the rate of reduction in ascorbic acid increases with the decrease in thickness of packaging materials (i.e., PP 50 μ to PP 25 μ and LDPE 50 μ to LDPE 25 μ). The increasing trend of AA content at the beginning of storage might be due to degradation of the cell wall as the ripening proceeds, providing substrates for AA synthesis [18]. As, it is recorded that mature harvested capsicum still progresses through the normal ripening process, although being non-climacteric in post-harvest respiratory patterns [19]. The reduction in AA content as days prolongs could be attributed to rapid conversion of L-ascorbic acid into dihydro-ascorbic acid in the presence of L-ascorbic acid oxidase and other oxidizing enzymes like peroxidase, catalase, and polyphenol oxidase [20]. The steep drop in AA content in control capsicum may be due to the huge susceptibility of ascorbic acid to oxidative deterioration, which occurred at an accelerated rate in control as the reaction is strongly favored by higher concentrations of O_2 as compared to polyethylene packages. The PP 50 μ showed maximum retention of AA content, which might be due to reduced respiration rate and other undesirable metabolic changes caused by atmospheric modification of low O_2 and high CO_2 inside the film, which concomitantly decreased the enzymatic oxidation of ascorbic acid. The result is in near agreement with Sahoo et al., (2014b).

3.2. Physiological Weight Loss

Table 2 Effect of different packaging materials in percentage physiological weight loss of bell pepper

Treatments	5 th day	10 th day	15 th day	20 th day	25 th day
T1 (LDPE 25 μ)	0.58 ^{bc}	1.25 ^c	2.04 ^{ab}	2.96 ^c	3.71 ^b
T2 (LDPE 50 μ)	0.558 ^c	1.00 ^d	1.97 ^{ab}	2.91 ^c	3.69 ^b
T3 (PP 25 μ)	0.59 ^{bc}	1.28 ^{bc}	2.06 ^{ab}	3.05 ^{bc}	3.74 ^b
T4 (PP 50 μ)	0.554 ^c	0.91 ^d	1.75 ^b	2.88 ^c	3.64 ^b
T5(Cardboard box)	0.862 ^a	1.42 ^{abc}	2.09 ^{ab}	3.24 ^{ab}	4.02 ^a
T6 (Jute Sack)	0.84 ^{ab}	1.51 ^{ab}	2.11 ^{ab}	3.29 ^a	-
T7 (Control)	0.864 ^a	1.61 ^a	2.31 ^a	-	-
SEM	0.081	0.076	0.153	0.065	0.067
LSD _{0.05}	0.24*	0.23****	0.46*	0.2**	0.205****
CV (%)	20.4	8.1	10.4	3.6	3.0

SEM, Standard Error of mean; CV, Coefficient of variation; LSD, least significant difference. Means in the column with the same letter (s) in superscript indicate no significant difference between treatments at 0.05 level of significance; **** Significant at 0.001 level of Significance; *** Significant at 0.01 level of Significance; ** Significant at 0.05 level of Significance

Figure 6 Effects of packaging materials in physiological weight loss of bell pepper cv Indra at different days of storage

Physiological weight loss is directly equivalent to postharvest water loss and is also responsible for causing deterioration and decrease in visual quality over time in capsicum. It results in deleterious changes in firmness, turgidity, discoloration, flavor, and nutritional value of capsicum [22]. PWL can accelerate senescence, pathogen invasion, and susceptibility to chilling injuries on fruits and vegetables as well. So, assessment of

percentage physiological weight loss holds paramount importance to estimate the quality and shelf life of capsicum. The interaction effect of packaging materials with percentage PWL over storage days showed a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in each day of measurement (Table 2). The percentage PWL, typically, increases along with ascending storage days, notably slowly in the beginning and at a relatively faster pace as the storage period increases (Fig 6). On the 5th day of storage, the capsicum packed in PP 50 μ recorded significantly least weight loss (0.554%) and was found at par with capsicum packed in LDPE 50 μ (0.558%), LDPE 25 μ (0.58%) and PP 25 μ (0.59%). Likewise, on the 10th and 15th day, the capsicum wrapped in PP 50 μ showed the least physiological loss in weight, i.e. 0.91% and 1.75% respectively as compared to other packaging materials under ambient room conditions. In parallel, the PP 50 μ showed its supremacy of having the least weight loss on 20th and 25th days of storage as well, and seen statistically similar with LDPE 50 μ , LDPE 25 μ , and PP 25 μ respectively. However, comparatively highest physiological loss in weight i.e., 0.86%, 1.61% and 2.31% on 5th, 10th and 15th day of storage period respectively was observed in unwrapped capsicum taken as control. Basically, the breakdown of carbohydrates into carbon dioxide and volatile vapor during the process of respiration and excessive moisture loss from capsicum tissues in transpiration could be the reason behind physiological weight loss. The capsicum packed in PP 50 μ was found best in reducing the physiological loss in weight, this might be because of low water vapor and gaseous permeability of PP films in contrast to LDPE films. PP film limits the rate of respiration and maintains the higher relative humidity inside the wrappers. These results are in conformity with the findings of Asgar (2020) where polypropylene packages showed the smallest weight loss than that of polyethylene packaging, wrapping and control.

3.3. Shelf life

Table 3 Effect of different packaging materials in the shelf life of bell pepper

Treatments	Shelf Life
T1 (LDPE 25 μ)	32.33 ^{ab}
T2 (LDPE 50 μ)	32.67 ^{ab}
T3 (PP 25 μ)	30.43 ^{ab}
T4 (PP 50 μ)	34.64 ^a
T5 (Cardboard box)	29.85 ^b
T6 (Jute Sack)	24.00 ^b
T7 (Control)	17.33 ^c
SEM	1.75
LSD _{0.05}	5.29***
CV (%)	10.4

SEM, Standard Error of mean; CV, Coefficient of variation; LSD, least significant difference. Means in the column with the same letter (s) in superscript indicate no significant difference between treatments at 0.05 level of significance; '****' Significant at 0.001 level of Significance

The shelf life of capsicum is the duration where it remains acceptable to eat. Everis (2017) claimed that within the shelf life the food can remain safe and retain the desired sensory, chemical, physical and microbiological characteristics. Therefore, apprehending the shelf life of capsicum is mandatory to assure its safety and quality. The different packaging materials had a highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$) impact on the shelf life of capsicum (Table 3). The longest shelf life of 34.64 days was monitored in capsicum packed in PP 50 μ film followed by LDPE 50 μ (32.67 days), LDPE 25 μ (32.33days), and PP 25 μ (30.43 days). Furthermore, the shortest shelf life was recorded in the control capsicum of 17.33 days. The maximal shelf life in PP 50 μ packed capsicum might be because it provides high water vapor and gaseous barrier compared to LDPE packaging films. Lazić et al. (2010) asserted that PP 40 μ has 2997.6 CO₂ and 1130.8 ml/m²/day, plbar O₂ permeability while LDPE 50 μ has 17612.0 CO₂ and 3058.2 ml/m²/day, plbar O₂ permeability. Likewise, Mangaraj et al. (2015) reported the water vapor transmissivity of 4.91 g/m².day in PP 45 μ and 11.67 g/m².day in LDPE 40 μ packaging films at 38°C and 90% RH. Therefore, lower gaseous permeability in PP 50 μ reduces respiration and retards the oxidation process, creating the micro climatic condition of lower O₂ and higher CO₂, ultimately prolonging the shelf life of capsicum. Furthermore, a strong moisture barrier within PP 50 μ increases RH inside the films, reduces water loss through transpiration and maintains high turgor pressure and consequently increasing the shelf life of capsicum. Similarly, the shortest shelf life of control capsicum might be due to excessive respiration and transpiration in open conditions which can lead to dehydration, wilting, loss of firmness, and decrease in visual quality.

4. Conclusions

This study showed that different packaging materials used, significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) affected shelf life and biochemical properties of capsicum namely TSS, TA, vitamin C, pH, and firmness at the time of storage. The micro-atmospheric modification created inside packaging materials appreciably reduced weight loss and retained both freshness and visual quality of capsicum. Among the treatments, PP and LDPE packaging films were found more effective in prolonging shelf life and maintaining the quality of stored bell-peppers. Furthermore, PP 50 μ packaging film proved to be ideal for storage based on prevention of decay, minimizing weight loss, and increasing shelf life followed by LDPE 50 μ . However, the almost negligible pungent odor was detected during the unwrapping of PP 50 μ and LDPE 50 μ at the end of the storage. Thus, the promotion of PP and LDPE packaging among farmers and retailers may improve the marketability, utility, and ultimately profitability of capsicum.

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